

Prediction of retail chain failure: examples of recent U.S. retail failures

Shawn Berry, DBA^{1*}

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¹William Howard Taft University, Lakewood CO, USA

*Correspondence: shawnpberry@gmail.com

Abstract Over the last several years, several prominent brick-and-mortar retail chains have ceased operations, raising concerns that some have referred to as the retail apocalypse. Scholars have attempted to model the likelihood of firm failure using various approaches. This study examines the failures of Bed Bath and Beyond, J.C. Penney, Rite Aid, and Sears Holdings in the United States between 2013 and 2022. Retail failure models that consider internal and external firm factors using both annual reports and macroeconomic data were analyzed and evaluated using logistic regression, PCA, and Random Forest approaches. The findings suggest that EBITDA/Revenue and annual average U.S. inflation rates are strong predictors of retail failure across various modeling approaches. The modeling results provide an early warning signal at least one to two years before failure, with accuracies of 93.8% to 96.9%.

Keywords: retail failure, financial ratios, retail, bankruptcy, retail apocalypse

1. Introduction

The number of high-profile retail chain failures over the last few years, including prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, has created concerns for not just employees of these retailers but also suppliers, investors, and property managers who become exposed to the financial consequences of such failures. Scholars have often referred to this phenomenon as a retail apocalypse (Peterson, 2017; Mende, 2019; Kaulfing and Neuenschwander, 2020). There are various sources of retail chain failure. In fact, Habib et al. (2020) identify three broad categories of factors, specifically “(i) firm-level fundamental determinants, (ii) macroeconomic determinants and (iii) firm-level corporate governance determinants” (p.1023). Jo and Shin (2016) observed that “financial ratios do not contain environmental factors, such as external economic situations. Therefore, using only financial ratios may be insufficient in constructing a bankruptcy prediction model because they essentially reflect past corporate internal accounting information while neglecting recent information” (p.33). Indeed, Rezende et al. (2017) modeled the financial distress of firms that went bankrupt, and noted that “the relationship between the phenomena of bankruptcy and financial distress is verified, using financial and macroeconomic explanatory variables.” However, because the underlying reasons for failure are unique to the circumstances of any retailer and seldom the same for other firms, some studies have pointed to aspects of a business that may precipitate failure. Habib et al. (2020) identify five such categories of circumstances, namely, “(i) financial reporting and auditing consequences, (ii) firm-level operational consequences, (iii) capital market consequences and (iv) corporate governance consequences” (p.1023). Kaufinger and Neuenschwander (2020) suggest that a retailer may be able to avoid failure by considering the accounting methodology used for inventory valuation. Redd and Vickerie (2017) suggest that the technological change for traditional brick-and-mortar retailers to transition to e-commerce

was perhaps a challenge. Lawrence, Pai, and Kleinman (2009) examined high-profile retail failures in the United States. Such modeling is valuable to business leaders and analysts to help assess the possibility of bankruptcy risk through the evaluation of “accounting variables such as inventories, liabilities, receivables, net income (loss), and revenue” (Lawrence, Pai, & Kleinman, 2009, p.61). While there is no singular cause of retail failure, each of these studies adds valuable insights into the underlying problems that precipitate failure. Therefore, the ability to anticipate and predict the possibility of failure is important for those who are ultimately affected to mitigate the risk (Keener, 2013).

As a result of these insights, scholars have created prediction models to quantify the likelihood of retail firm failure. Some models rely on ratios based on assets, particularly the Altman Z-score model (Altman, 1968), whereas others generally use various combinations of other firms’ financial ratios (Altman et al., 2014; Brédart, 2014; Evans and Mathur, 2014). Although the Altman model has been widely used to predict bankruptcy, it is not without shortcomings (Celli, 2015; Salimi, 2015). First, although Altman’s (1968) model is based on manufacturing firms, scholars have been critical of its applicability to retail firm failure. Hayes, Hodge, and Hughes (2010), in their analysis of failed retail firms (n=17), noted that although the Z-score model was generally accurate in its predictions of failure for these firms, “two firms were misclassified yet later revealed potential financial distress” (p.122). Li (2012) also noted that “all models tend to have high type II error of mis-predicting a solvent firm as bankrupt. There appears to be a need to develop a model for predicting solvent firms” (p.39). Second, the context in which the Altman model is used may be inappropriate for certain industries. Hayes et al. (2010) highlighted the shortcomings of the Z-score model by declaring that although “the formula has been demonstrated to be fairly predictive in a variety of contexts and cultural settings, it is not designed for use in every situation. Variations of Altman’s Z encompass publicly versus privately held firms and manufacturing versus privately held nonmanufacturing firms” (p.132). Indeed, Grice and Ingram (2001) declared that the Altman Z-score model was not “as useful for predicting financial stress conditions other than bankruptcy as it is for predicting bankruptcy” (p.53). Finally, the temporal aspect of Altman’s (1968) model is noted as a shortcoming in the literature. Grice and Ingram (2001) concluded that the Altman (1968) model is not “as useful for predicting bankruptcy in recent periods as it was for the periods in which it was developed and tested by Altman” (p.53). Because of these shortcomings, scholars have expressed the need for alternative methods to predict firm failure (Hayes et al., 2010; Li, 2012). Thus, the objective of this study is to advance an alternative and novel means of predicting retail firm failure to fill this knowledge gap, and to overcome the shortcomings of the Z-score model with regard to misclassification. It is hoped that this alternative approach will conceptually have greater generalizability to other industry settings beyond retail.

Rather than examining the fluctuating value of a firm’s assets using asset-based ratios, this study uses revenue-based ratios to evaluate the failure risk with respect to a firm’s costs and debt levels as internal factors. Scholars assert that firm revenue is more relevant to investors as a performance measure (Ghosh et al., 2005; Huang et al., 2015; Zhang, 2005). Indeed, Arlov, Rankov, and Kotlica (2013) observed that “unhealthy companies were characterized by depreciating cash flows from operating, investing and financing cash flows about one or two years before they filed for bankruptcy” (p.88), suggesting that revenue-based ratios are more useful than ratios based on assets. Furthermore, profitability will also be measured as a ratio of revenue to predict firm failure. Li et al. (2022) examined “five dimensions: solvency, profitability, operational capacity and development capacity as well as cash flow status of each firm” (p.28), and noted that “the results show that the profitability factor has the greatest contribution to the predictive role” (p.25).

This study also includes the effect of a firm’s external environment on failure, using key macroeconomic variables as predictors, as in Keener (2013) and Ceylan (2021). In their study of the external factors that affect firm solvency, Kiyak and Pranckevičiūtė (2017) “determined a statistically significant

relationship between companies' solvency" (p.64) and, among other things, the rates of inflation and interest in an economy. Another external factor for a firm is the effect of consumers' attitudes or feelings toward the firm and how they are ultimately interpreted by investors in the firm. Consumer satisfaction, as measured by the American Consumer Satisfaction Index (ACSI), has been shown to influence firm returns and risk levels such "that positive changes (i.e., improvement) in customer satisfaction result in negative changes (i.e., reduction) in overall and downside systematic and idiosyncratic risk" (Tuli and Bharadwaj, 2009, p.184). The ACSI score has also been validated by Peng et al. (2014) since this metric exerts influence on stock investors, and therefore, influences the returns of firms, noting that "customer satisfaction is value-relevant for both investors and firm management, particularly in pessimistic periods" (p.827). With respect to how a firm is valued on the stock market, Ittner, Larcker, and Taylor (2009) suggest that while "we find that ACSI scores provide some incremental information on future operating income and that the market quickly responds to the release of information on large increases in satisfaction...we find no evidence that ACSI predicts long-run returns" (p.826). More importantly, Fornell, Morgeson, and Hult (2016) found that "customer satisfaction has an effect on earnings themselves" (p.92). Interestingly, Alan and Lapré (2018) observed that, among airline passengers, the "propensity to complain (is) positively associated with future financial distress" (p.747). Alan and Lapré (2018) studied financial distress among airline firms and found "that financial metrics do not fully explain the future financial performance of a firm and that operational performance can be a leading indicator of financial performance" (p.753). In particular, Alan and Lapré (2018) examined how firms managed their revenue, service quality, and efficiency, and found that firms' financial distress was associated with poor revenue management, poor service quality, and operational inefficiency. Although their study was not related to retail firms, the observations of Alan and Lapré (2018) can generally be considered to be related to other industry sectors, because poor financial performance almost always has common and fundamental roots. Finally, the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on firm failure is examined using a dummy variable as a proxy for external factors that represent unpredictable events that impact consumers and businesses. These insights form the basis of the framework employed in this study to predict retail firm failure, which is an alternative to the Z-score model.

In this short paper, data from recent high-profile, multi-store retail chain failures between 2013 and 2022, specifically, Bed Bath and Beyond, J.C. Penney, Rite Aid, and Sears Holdings were used to create retail failure models. The study used three different modeling approaches: logistic regression, principal component analysis (PCA), and Random Forest. The selected key financial data are drawn from annual reports to construct internal firm factors, and the selected macroeconomic indicators are used as external firm factors. The correlates of failure were explored, and predictive models of failure were created and evaluated using significant internal and external firm factors to estimate the probabilities of failure for each firm over the sample period. Unlike other studies that incorporate paired samples of failed and non-failed firms to construct their models (Altman et al., 2014; Brédart, 2014; Hayes, Hodge, & Hughes, 2010; McGurr & Devaney, 1998), in this study, the sample data from each firm are coded according to whether failure has occurred for each year of operation. This study compared the merits of logistic regression, principal component analysis (PCA), and machine learning methods. Most scholars tend to agree that logistic regression analysis is appropriate for binary outcomes (failure or non-failure), because the method "is more reliable" (Ballkoci and Gremi, 2017, p.137), and was used in a similar study by Lawrence, Pai and Kleinman (2009) and Rezende et al. (2017). However, with the advances in big data, machine learning has enabled researchers to discover new relationships within datasets with high accuracy (Aktan, 2011; Barboza et al., 2017). Logistic regression and PCA was used by Li et al. (2022) and "achieves 86% prediction accuracy" (p.25). In their study, Alaminos and Fernández (2016) reported the accuracy of multiple discriminant analysis (MDA) to be between 77% and 87.8% for neural networks and between 81.2% and 100% and of logit to be between 54% and 97.1%, respectively. The authors caution "that more modern methods do not always guarantee the best results. As such, there are no definitive conclusions as to which methodology is

most precise for constructing models” (Alaminos and Fernández, 2016, p.3). Finally, the paper concludes with a discussion of the results and directions for future research.

2. Materials and Methods

The data used in this study were obtained from various secondary sources. First, company data were drawn from publicly available SEC 10-K annual report filings for Bed Bath and Beyond (2015-2022), J.C. Penney (2013-2020), Rite Aid (2013-2022) and Sears Holdings (2013-2018) for revenue, costs, and store counts to examine the internal factors of failure. Failure of a firm was coded as 0 in years when that firm was still in operation and coded as 1 for the year in which failure occurred. External factors are represented by key macroeconomic indicators. The annual average US interest rate is used as a moderating variable for failure. The annual average US inflation rate was used as a mediating variable for failure. The occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic was used as a mediating variable and coded each year in the study, with 0 representing no pandemic and 1 representing pandemic conditions. The consumer satisfaction ratings for each chain were published using the American Consumer Satisfaction Index (ACSI) as a proxy for the extent of the appeal of the retail chain to consumers. Internal factors are represented by key financial metrics that rely on cost and revenue. Revenue is used as a measure of sales performance. The cost of revenue, selling, and general administration (SGA) costs were used as measures of the firm’s effectiveness in controlling its own internal costs for selling. Long-term debt is used as a measure of debt default potential. Finally, EBITDA is used as a measure of firm profitability. The costs were then calculated as the ratios of revenue for each year. Figure 1 illustrates the methodological framework of this study. Table 1 presents these variables.

Table 1. Variable list

Variable Name	Description	Model role	Variable type
Fail (1=yes)	Outcome: 1=failed, 0=not failed	Dependent	Binary
Number of stores	Number of stores reported in filing	Independent	Continuous
US interest rate (%)	Average annual US interest rate	Independent	Continuous
US inflation rate (%)	Average annual US inflation rate	Independent	Continuous
EBITDA/Revenue (\$M)	Profitability as a fraction of revenue	Independent	Continuous
SGA/Revenue (\$M)	Selling & General Administration as a fraction of revenue	Mediating	Continuous
Cost of revenue/Revenue (\$M)	Cost of revenue as a fraction of revenue	Mediating	Continuous
Long-term debt/Revenue (\$M)	Mediated by US interest rate (%)	Mediating	Continuous
Pandemic (1= yes)	COVID-19 year: 1=yes, 0=no	Mediating	Binary
ACSI score	ACSI annual consumer satisfaction rating	Moderating	Discrete

Figure 1. Methodological framework

3. Results

The sample data were analyzed and modelled.

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics for the sample data with the means, standard deviations, and Shapiro-Wilk test statistics. This table is important for evaluating the degree of variability in data. Revenue appears to have the highest variation among retail firms. Among the cost factors, the cost of revenue showed the highest variation, followed by SGA, and long-term debt. When the variables are scaled with revenue, EBITDA/Revenue has the lowest mean, and SGA/Revenue has the lowest standard deviation.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation	Shapiro-Wilk (p-value)
Revenue	16854.81 (M\$)	8105.03	0.945 (0.107)
SGA	4450.66 (M\$)	1730.76	0.929 (0.036)
Cost of revenue	12301.91 (M\$)	6545.78	0.909 (0.011)
EBITDA	191.16 (M\$)	955.70	0.934 (0.050)
Stores	1891.81	1194.25	0.816 (<0.001)
US interest rate	2.16%	0.58	0.921 (0.022)
US inflation rate	2.11%	1.85	0.720 (<0.001)
ACSI score	76.31	3.11	0.959 (0.257)
Long-term debt	3475.12 (M\$)	1680.49	0.934 (0.049)
Pandemic	0.22	0.42	0.512 (<0.001)
SGA/Revenue	0.29	0.07	0.938 (0.066)
Cost of revenue/Revenue	0.71	0.7	0.915 (0.016)
EBITDA/Revenue	-0.012	0.14	0.625 (<0.001)
Long-term debt/Revenue	0.30	0.50	0.339 (<0.001)

Source: data analysis

3.2 Sample data

Table 3 presents the sample data.

Table 3. Retail chain failures and key firm financial and macroeconomic indicators

Chain	Year	Fail 1=yes	Revenue (\$M)	Cost of revenue (\$M)	SGA (\$M)	EBITDA (\$M)	Stores	US interest rate (%)	US inflation rate (%)	SGA/ Revenue	Cost of revenue/ Revenue	Long- term debt (\$M)	Long- term debt/ Revenue	Pandemic 1= yes	ACSI score	EBITDA/ Revenue
Bed Bath & Beyond	2015	0	12,104	7,484	3,205	1,689	1513	2.1	0.12	0.26	0.62	1500	0.12	0	75	0.14
Bed Bath & Beyond	2016	0	12,216	7,639	3,441	1,426	1530	1.8	1.26	0.28	0.63	1492	0.12	0	79	0.12
Bed Bath & Beyond	2017	0	12,349	7,906	3,682	1,074	1546	2.3	2.13	0.3	0.64	1492	0.12	0	76	0.09
Bed Bath & Beyond	2018	0	12,029	7,925	3,681	251.69	1552	2.9	2.44	0.31	0.66	1488	0.12	0	79	0.02
Bed Bath & Beyond	2019	0	11,159	7,617	3,732	-357.55	1533	2.1	1.81	0.33	0.68	1488	0.13	0	80	-0.03
Bed Bath & Beyond	2020	0	9,233	6,115	3,224	81.06	1500	0.9	1.23	0.35	0.66	1488	0.16	1	79	0.01
Bed Bath & Beyond	2021	0	7,868	5,384	2,692	-114.33	1020	1.5	4.7	0.34	0.68	1190	0.15	1	80	-0.01
Bed Bath & Beyond	2022	1	5,345	4,130	2,373	- 2,992.29	953	3	8	0.44	0.77	1180	0.22	1	78	-0.56
Rite Aid	2013	0	25,526	18,203	6,561	1,079	4570	2.4	1.62	0.26	0.71	5708	0.22	0	74	0.04
Rite Aid	2014	0	26,528	18,952	6,696	1,241	4623	2.5	1.46	0.25	0.71	5459	0.21	0	78	0.05
Rite Aid	2015	0	20,770	15,778	4,581	762.24	4561	2.1	0.12	0.22	0.76	6967	0.34	0	69	0.04
Rite Aid	2016	0	22,928	17,863	4,777	655.92	4536	1.8	1.26	0.21	0.78	3273	0.14	0	78	0.03
Rite Aid	2017	0	21,529	16,749	4,651	1,838	2550	2.3	2.13	0.22	0.78	3371	0.16	0	77	0.09
Rite Aid	2018	0	21,640	16,963	4,592	240.87	2469	2.9	2.44	0.21	0.78	3479	0.16	0	76	0.01
Rite Aid	2019	0	21,928	17,202	4,587	493.37	2461	2.1	1.81	0.21	0.78	5807	0.26	0	75	0.02
Rite Aid	2020	0	24,043	19,339	4,657	417.45	2510	0.9	1.23	0.19	0.8	5909	0.25	1	72	0.02
Rite Aid	2021	0	24,568	19,462	5,034	-54.97	2450	1.5	4.7	0.2	0.79	5345	0.22	1	71	0.00
Rite Aid	2022	1	24,092	19,288	4,902	-255.42	2450	3	8	0.2	0.8	5311	0.22	1	80	-0.01
Sears Holdings	2013	0	36188	27433	9384	-487	2429	2.4	1.62	0.26	0.76	2531	0.07	0	77	-0.01
Sears Holdings	2014	0	31198	24049	8220	-718	1725	2.5	1.46	0.26	0.77	2878	0.09	0	73	-0.02

Sears Holdings	2015	0	25146	19336	6857	-836	1672	2.1	0.12	0.27	0.77	1971	0.08	0	71	-0.03
Sears Holdings	2016	0	22138	15184	6109	-808	1430	1.8	1.26	0.28	0.69	3470	0.16	0	77	-0.04
Sears Holdings	2017	0	16702	11349	5139	-562	1002	2.3	2.13	0.31	0.68	2199	0.13	0	73	-0.03
Sears Holdings	2018	1	6709	5899	2626	-571	332	2.9	2.44	0.39	0.88	2239	0.33	0	73	-0.09
JC Penney	2013	0	11859	8367	4114	-819	1094	2.4	1.62	0.35	0.71	4839	0.41	0	79	-0.07
JC Penney	2014	0	12257	7996	3993	323	1062	2.5	1.46	0.33	0.65	5227	0.43	0	77	0.03
JC Penney	2015	0	12625	8074	3775	654	1021	2.1	0.12	0.3	0.64	4668	0.37	0	74	0.05
JC Penney	2016	0	12547	8071	3538	926	1013	1.8	1.26	0.28	0.64	4339	0.35	0	82	0.07
JC Penney	2017	0	12554	8208	3845	935	872	2.3	2.13	0.31	0.65	3780	0.30	0	79	0.07
JC Penney	2018	0	11664	7870	3596	568	864	2.9	2.44	0.31	0.67	3716	0.32	0	77	0.05
JC Penney	2019	0	10716	7013	3585	583	849	2.1	1.81	0.33	0.65	3826	0.36	0	78	0.05
JC Penney	2020	1	1196	813	572	-546	846	0.9	1.23	0.48	0.68	3574	2.99	1	76	-0.46

3.3. Regression analysis:

The sample data were analyzed using logistic regression analysis..

Figure 2 illustrates the correlation matrix for the dataset. The correlation coefficients between the variables are listed in the table. Using this table, we can identify strong relationships between the independent and dependent variables. The dependent variable fail appears to be strongly and positively correlated with EBITDA/Revenue, long-term debt/Revenue, the annual average US inflation rate, if the year was a COVID-19 pandemic year (yes=1), and SGA/Revenue. This observation suggests that failure is certainly linked to profitability, debt, and selling costs as internal factors, and inflation and the pandemic as externalities. EBITDA/Revenue appears to be the greatest predictor of firm failure. Although there is some multicollinearity among the strongly correlated independent variables, the variables with the least multicollinearity were EBITDA/Revenue, SGA/Revenue, and the US inflation rate. These variables can be considered a good group of correlates of firm failure because they reflect the state of critical firm factors and the influence of the macroeconomy on failure during periods of high inflation.

Figure 2. Correlation matrix of dataset

	Year	Fail (1=yes)	Revenue (\$M)	Cost of revenue (\$M)	SGA (\$M)	EBITDA (\$M)	Number of stores	US interest rate (%)	US inflation rate (%)	SGA/ Revenue	Cost of revenue/ Revenue	Long-term debt (\$M)	EBITDA/ Revenue	Long-term debt/ Revenue	Pandemic (1= yes)	ACSI score
Year	1.00	0.49	-0.39	-0.32	-0.55	-0.31	-0.28	-0.20	0.67	0.19	0.20	-0.18	-0.40	0.18	0.75	0.17
Fail (1=yes)	0.49	1.00	-0.36	-0.28	-0.41	-0.52	-0.24	0.19	0.58	0.50	0.39	-0.09	-0.73	0.49	0.49	0.05
Revenue (\$M)	-0.39	-0.36	1.00	0.99	0.93	0.11	0.65	0.12	-0.11	-0.79	0.46	0.38	0.35	-0.42	-0.21	-0.35
Cost of revenue (\$M)	-0.32	-0.28	0.99	1.00	0.90	0.06	0.65	0.11	-0.05	-0.78	0.56	0.39	0.29	-0.38	-0.14	-0.38
SGA (\$M)	-0.55	-0.41	0.93	0.90	1.00	-0.01	0.48	0.21	-0.17	-0.58	0.31	0.21	0.32	-0.47	-0.34	-0.28
EBITDA (\$M)	-0.31	-0.52	0.11	0.06	-0.01	1.00	0.35	-0.14	-0.48	-0.49	-0.35	0.26	0.79	-0.12	-0.39	0.04
Number of stores	-0.28	-0.24	0.65	0.65	0.48	0.35	1.00	-0.01	-0.12	-0.65	0.34	0.50	0.25	-0.19	-0.10	-0.26
US interest rate (%)	-0.20	0.19	0.12	0.11	0.21	-0.14	-0.01	1.00	0.35	-0.03	0.19	-0.05	0.01	-0.37	-0.45	0.08
US inflation rate (%)	0.67	0.58	-0.11	-0.05	-0.17	-0.48	-0.12	0.35	1.00	0.12	0.32	-0.10	-0.45	-0.09	0.59	0.29
SGA/ Revenue	0.19	0.50	-0.79	-0.78	-0.58	-0.49	-0.65	-0.03	0.12	1.00	-0.32	-0.46	-0.67	0.54	0.20	0.27
Cost of revenue/ Revenue	0.20	0.39	0.46	0.56	0.31	-0.35	0.34	0.19	0.32	-0.32	1.00	0.25	-0.24	-0.11	0.20	-0.43
Long-term debt (\$M)	-0.18	-0.09	0.38	0.39	0.21	0.26	0.50	-0.05	-0.10	-0.46	0.25	1.00	0.18	0.13	-0.02	-0.31
EBITDA/ Revenue	-0.40	-0.73	0.35	0.29	0.32	0.79	0.25	0.01	-0.45	-0.67	-0.24	0.18	1.00	-0.57	-0.51	0.00
Long-term debt/ Revenue	0.18	0.49	-0.42	-0.38	-0.47	-0.12	-0.19	-0.37	-0.09	0.54	-0.11	0.13	-0.57	1.00	0.32	-0.01
Pandemic (1= yes)	0.75	0.49	-0.21	-0.14	-0.34	-0.39	-0.10	-0.45	0.59	0.20	0.20	-0.02	-0.51	0.32	1.00	0.04
ACSI score	0.17	0.05	-0.35	-0.38	-0.28	0.04	-0.26	0.08	0.29	0.27	-0.43	-0.31	0.00	-0.01	0.04	1.00

Source: data analysis

The impact of the selected external factors on the firm is examined with respect to the likelihood of retail chain failure. The dependent variable, fail, was once again modelled using logistic regression. Table 4 presents the results of the analysis. The American Consumer Satisfaction Index (ACSI) score for retail chains represents a proxy for consumer preferences for retail chains. For the existence of the COVID-19 pandemic, a binary dummy variable (1= yes) was examined, and non-COVID-19 pandemic years were coded as zero. Finally, the annual average US interest rate and annual average US inflation rate were used to evaluate the effects of the macroeconomy on the likelihood of retail chain failure. Surprisingly, ACSI was not a statistically significant predictor of failure. The most statistically significant model had the annual average US inflation rate as an independent variable, with both the intercept and slope parameters being significant ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.05$, respectively). The model that evaluated the effect of the existence of a pandemic on failure in any given year also had a statistically significant intercept and slope parameter at $p=0.001$ and $p=0.05$, respectively. Finally, the model that evaluates the effect of the annual average US interest rates had a statistically significant intercept coefficient at the $p=0.1$ level. The pandemic model implies that, when there is a pandemic, retail chains are 17 times more likely to fail than when there is no pandemic. The inflation model implies that, with a 1% increase in the annual average US rate of inflation, retail chains are twice as likely to fail. Finally, the interest rate model implies that retail firms are just over three times more likely to fail, with a 1% increase in the annual average US interest rates, retail firms are just over 3.5 times more likely to fail. The ACSI model implies that changes in the ACSI score for a retail chain do not significantly change the likelihood of failure for the firm ($\exp(0.0555) = 1.05$) and that consumer attitudes toward a chain are not a singular determinant of the likelihood of failure.

Table 4. Logistic regression results with external factors. Dependent variable: fail.

Estimates	ACSI	Pandemic	US interest rate	US inflation rate
Intercept	-6.191	-3.178 (**)	-4.856 (.)	-3.957 (***)
(p-value)	(0.657)	(0.0019)	(0.096)	(<0.001)
[s.e.]	[13.947]	[1.021]	[2.918]	[1.164]
Slope	0.056	2.890 (*)	1.267	0.708 (*)
(p-value)	(0.760)	(0.023)	(0.286)	(0.021)
[s.e.]	[0.182]	[1.275]	[1.187]	[0.307]
AIC	28.017	21.958	26.757	20.349

$p < 0.1$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Source : data analysis

The effect of the selected internal factors on the likelihood of failure was examined using logistic regression modelling. The results of logistic regression analysis are presented in Table 5. Revenue and various cost measures were used as independent variables. The costs of revenue, selling, and general administration (SGA) are used as proxies to represent a firm's ability to control costs. The number of stores represents the scale of the operations in the retail chain. Finally, long-term debt is used as a measure of a firm's level of indebtedness, beyond the costs of selling and generating revenue. The failure model with EBITDA as an independent variable was the only model with the lowest AIC, and the intercept ($p=0.004$) and slope ($p=0.086$) parameters were statistically significant at 0.001 and 0.1, respectively. Although the intercepts were not statistically significant, Revenue and SGA were statistically significant at 0.1 ($p=0.079$ and $p=0.057$, respectively). The number of stores does not indicate that the physical scale of retail chain operations is significant. Surprisingly, the level of long-term debt and the cost of revenue were also not statistically significant predictors of failure.

Table 5. Logistic regression results with internal factors. Dependent variable: fail.

Estimates	Revenue	SGA	Cost of revenue	Stores	EBITDA	Long-term debt
Intercept	0.757	3.546	-0.114	-0.02467	-2.494 (**)	-1.374
(p-value)	(0.583)	(0.193)	(0.009)	(0.986)	(0.0036)	(0.247)
[s.e.]	[1.379]	[2.725]	[3.576]	[1.376]	[0.858]	[1.186]
Slope	-0.0002 (.)	-0.0015 (.)	-0.00019	-0.0013	-0.0022 (.)	-0.0002
(p-value)	(0.079)	(0.057)	(0.154)	(0.207)	(0.086)	(0.608)
[s.e.]	[0.0001]	[0.0008]	[0.0001]	[0.001]	[0.0013]	[0.0003]
AIC	23.039	20.172	25.095	25.277	19.806	27.841

$p < 0.1$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Source : data analysis

Logistic regression models of retail chain failure were created by transforming key independent variables into fractions of revenue to create revenue ratios. Table 6 presents the results of the analysis. All the models had statistically significant intercepts and slope parameters. The model with the highest levels of statistical significance had SGA/Revenue as an independent variable, with the intercept being significant at 0.001 ($p=0.009$) and the slope parameter significant at 0.05 ($p=0.028$). The model with EBITDA/Revenue, although having a lower AIC, had an intercept that was significant at 0.001, and the slope was significant at 0.1. The failure model using SGA/Revenue implies that for a 1 unit increase in this ratio, the likelihood of failure will increase substantially.

Table 6. Logistic regression results with internal factors as ratios of revenue. Dependent variable: fail.

Estimates	SGA/ Revenue	Cost of revenue/ Revenue	EBITDA/ Revenue	Long-term debt/ Revenue
Intercept	-9.245 (**)	-17.021 (*)	-3.264 (**)	-3.238 (*)
(p-value)	(0.009)	(0.043)	(0.009)	(0.041)
[s.e.]	[3.576]	[8.404]	[1.259]	[1.584]
Slope	22.728 (*)	20.253 (.)	-41.769 (.)	4.274
(p-value)	(0.028)	(0.064)	(0.089)	(0.459)
[s.e.]	[10.357]	[10.932]	[24.599]	[5.768]
AIC	20.76	23.131	13.951	23.175

$p < 0.1$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Source : data analysis

Using insights from previous analyses, a failure-prediction model was created for the failure of the dependent variable. Unfortunately, because the use of binomial logistic regression was not effective in this case owing to convergence problems, the model was estimated using penalized maximum likelihood logistic regression (Zhang et al., 2021). Table 7 presents the results of the analysis. The independent variables used were the US inflation rate, long-term debt/Revenue, and EBITDA/Revenue. The Wald test statistic for the model was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), implying that the variables were good contributors to the model fit. Multicollinearity among variables is addressed using variance inflation factors (VIF), and is reported in Table 7. The VIF score “is a measure of how much the variance of a regression coefficient is increased due to collinearity” (Rdocumentation.com, n.d.), and informs the researcher as to which variables might be safely omitted from a model without compromising its explanatory power, given a maximum threshold VIF score. The thresholds for VIF are “as a rule of thumb, a VIF value that exceeds 5 or 10 indicates a problematic amount of collinearity” (James et al., 2021, p.102), and note that “Typically in practice there is a small amount of collinearity among the predictors” (James et al., 2021, p.102). Given that the variance inflation factors (VIF) reported in Table 7 are below 5.0, this suggests that the observations are sufficiently independent to avoid significant multicollinearity issues. Figure 3 illustrates the log odds plots. Log-odds plots were used to evaluate whether assumptions for logistic regression were met when the relationship between the independent variable and log odds of the dependent variable was linear in nature (Theobald et al., 2019). The linearity of log-odds plots suggests that there is a linear relationship between the US inflation rate and log-odds of the dependent variable fail, but not with EBITDA/Revenue or Long-term debt/Revenue, implying that the latter two are perhaps nonlinear in nature. However, these variables were retained because of their significance in predicting failure, as shown in an earlier analysis.

Table 7. Failure prediction model. Dependent variable: fail.

	Estimate	Std. Error	Chi-sq.	Pr (> t)	VIF
Intercept	-4.349	1.434	9.207	0.002	-
US inflation rate	0.592	0.297	3.971	0.046	1.71
Long-term debt/Revenue	1.374	1.057	1.689	0.194	2.61
EBITDA/Revenue	-1.606	4.303	0.139	0.709	2.34

Likelihood ratio test=13.81581 on 3 df, $p=0.003$, $n=32$

Wald test = 12.7042 on 3 df, $p = 0.005$

$p < 0.1$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Source: data analysis

Figure 3. Linearity of log-odds plot versus predictor variables

3.4 Random Forest analysis

To evaluate if other methods would be more accurate than logistic regression alone in predicting failure, a Random Forest model was created to predict retail failure. In laypersons' terms, Random Forest models leverage machine learning methods to find hidden relationships among variables by taking a dataset and iteratively sampling it using rules to sort and classify the data into groups according to common attributes and with minimal error (e.g., fail and non-fail) (Breiman, 2001). Once the sorting of the data has been exhausted, the data are effectively classified into desired groups according to the importance of these attributes (Breiman, 2001). The advantage of Random Forest modeling is that it is seen as a robust approach to prediction compared to logistic regression modeling techniques (Couronné, Probst, & Boulesteix, 2018). The model was trained with 25 samples and tested with seven samples using an 80-20 split of the dataset. The model was configured by default in the Random Forest package in R with 500 trees using the default of one-third of the predictors or four variables at each split (Saarinen, 2023). Table 8 illustrates the importance of the model features that best predict when the firm has not failed versus 11011 when it does. Among the failure instances, EBITDA/Revenue, SGA/Revenue, US interest rate, number of stores, and US inflation rate were the top five most important features that influenced the probability of failure. Surprisingly, the cost of revenue/Revenue did not rank very high in importance among the instances of failure and non-failure. These features are also important for predicting whether a firm will fail. The Random Forest model yielded an accuracy of 93.8% and an out-of-bag (OOB) error rate of 6.25%. The F1 score for the Random Forest model was 1, and precision and recall were 1.

Table 8. Feature importance

Variable	0 (has not failed)	1 (failed)	Mean Decrease Accuracy	Mean Decrease Gini
EBITDA/Revenue	7.840	7.111	8.019	1.575
Number of stores	3.582	3.429	3.740	0.585
US inflation rate (%)	4.318	3.278	4.459	0.995
US interest rate (%)	5.938	5.254	6.438	1.016
SGA/Revenue	8.306	6.877	8.238	1.542
Pandemic (1=yes)	-1.171	-0.472	-0.869	0.127
ACSI score	1.027	0.000	1.044	0.039
Cost of revenue/Revenue	0.642	2.794	2.044	0.589
Long-term debt/Revenue	-0.861	0.817	-0.538	0.215

Source: data analysis

3.5 Principal component analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed as an approach to model firm failure. PCA is a popular statistical method used to predict bankruptcy by transforming and reducing a large dataset with many correlated variables into one that is more convenient in terms of size (Prusak, 2020) into factors that explain the greatest amount of variance (Krabbe, 2016). The dataset was dimensionally reduced to include nine components. The cross-validation plot of the root mean squared error of prediction (RMSEP) in Table 9 indicates that three components would suffice for the model, given that the error increases beyond this point. Although a greater number of components would yield greater amounts of explained variance, as shown in Table 10, this PCA model explained 67.74% of the variance, with three components accounting for 72.47% of the data.

Table 9. Cross-validated MSE estimates by component

Metric	(Intercept)	1 comps	2 comps	3 comps	4 comps	5 comps	6 comps	7 comps	8 comps	9 comps
CV	0.3414	0.2627	0.2212	0.2088	0.2388	0.2376	0.2455	0.2960	0.3423	0.3794
adjCV	0.3414	0.2620	0.2176	0.2070	0.2354	0.2339	0.2427	0.2871	0.3307	0.3657

Source: data analysis

Table 10. Percentage of variance explained.

Variable	Comp_ 1	Comp_ 2	Comp_ 3	Comp_ 4	Comp_ 5	Comp_ 6	Comp_ 7	Comp_ 8	Comp_ 9
X	32.30	54.20	72.47	84.82	91.96	95.42	98.44	99.52	100.00
Fail..1.yes.	45.86	65.75	67.74	73.34	74.77	75.76	78.55	80.94	80.94

Source: data analysis

Table 11 illustrates the PCA model factor loadings and how the variables affected the prediction of retail firm failure. Component 1 is greatly influenced by EBITDA/Revenue and the number of stores because of their high positive loadings, as well as the negative loadings on SGA/Revenue, Long-term debt/Revenue, and the Pandemic. Component 1 suggests that financial efficiency and profitability are affected by the proportion of revenue related to debt and costs, the firm scale, and the negative impact of COVID-19. Component 2 could be considered a group of stressors on the firm that affect costs and are greatly influenced by the Cost of Revenue/Revenue and US inflation. Component 3 is significantly influenced by the US interest rate, US inflation rate, and ACSI score, suggesting that this component represents macroeconomic and consumer attitudes.

Table 11. Principal Component factor loadings

Variable	Comp 1	Comp 2	Comp 3	Comp 4	Comp 5	Comp 6	Comp 7	Comp 8	Comp 9
Number of stores	0.342	0.306	-0.226	0.129	0.703	0.305	-0.285	-0.220	0.000
Cost of revenue/Revenue	0.000	0.618	0.000	-0.242	0.000	-0.705	0.000	-0.216	0.000
US inflation rate (%)	-0.253	0.438	0.436	0.258	0.000	0.240	0.231	0.000	0.611
US interest rate (%)	0.127	0.126	0.619	-0.452	0.177	0.221	0.265	-0.152	-0.456
SGA/Revenue	-0.491	-0.234	0.000	-0.286	0.000	0.000	-0.418	-0.629	0.200
EBITDA/Revenue	0.485	-0.248	0.000	0.280	-0.190	0.000	0.397	-0.634	0.154
Long-term debt/Revenue	-0.395	0.000	-0.387	-0.200	0.428	0.000	0.670	0.000	0.000
Pandemic (1=yes)	-0.370	0.350	-0.172	0.476	-0.202	0.188	0.000	-0.281	-0.571
ACSI score	-0.173	-0.266	0.431	0.477	0.458	-0.499	0.000	0.000	-0.137

Source: data analysis

3.6 Estimating probability of firm failure

The probability of firm failure was estimated for each year of firm operation using each model approach, the results are displayed in Table 12. The probabilities are calculated by taking the odds ratio of the result of the dependent variable fail, as given by the following formula

$$P(\text{fail}) = \exp(\text{fail}) / (1 + \exp(\text{fail})).$$

The probability estimates from the Random Forest model generally appear to underestimate firm failure but also seem to correctly predict when failure occurs. However, the estimates from the PCA model under- and overestimated failures generally correctly predicted failure instances and signaled risk at least one year before failure. The penalized maximum likelihood model correctly predicted failure and provided strong early signals a year or two prior to failure. In the context of the firms themselves, the PCA and penalized maximum likelihood models worked well for Bed Bath and Beyond, Rite Aid, and JC Penney, suggesting that the failure of Sears Holdings was influenced by factors other than the variables in the framework of this study, such as corporate governance.

Table 12. Probability estimates of firm failure according to model approach

Year	Retailer	Fail (1=yes)	Pandemic (1= yes)	Random Forest	PCA (3 comps.)	Penalized Max. Likelihood
2015	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.284	0.017
2016	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.224	0.033
2017	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.061	0.056
2018	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	0.000	0.008	0.118	0.074
2019	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.021	0.059
2020	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	1.000	0.012	-0.027	0.043
2021	Bed Bath & Beyond	0.000	1.000	0.026	0.249	0.263
2022	Bed Bath & Beyond	1.000	1.000	0.880	0.913	0.884
2013	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.007	0.063
2014	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.012	0.054
2015	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.060	0.039
2016	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.002	-0.066	0.040
2017	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.104	0.063
2018	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.024	0.189	0.085
2019	Rite Aid	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.049	0.082
2020	Rite Aid	0.000	1.000	0.102	-0.017	0.056
2021	Rite Aid	0.000	1.000	0.036	0.214	0.304
2022	Rite Aid	1.000	1.000	0.686	0.678	0.760
2013	Sears Holdings	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.081	0.042
2014	Sears Holdings	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.042
2015	Sears Holdings	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.017	0.019
2016	Sears Holdings	0.000	0.000	0.702	-0.128	0.047
2017	Sears Holdings	0.000	0.000	0.076	0.009	0.070
2018	Sears Holdings	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.751	0.162
2019	Sears Holdings	-	0.000	-	-	-
2020	Sears Holdings	-	1.000	-	-	-
2021	Sears Holdings	-	1.000	-	-	-
2022	Sears Holdings	-	1.000	-	-	-
2013	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.240	0.130
2014	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.108	0.110
2015	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.012	-0.117	0.043
2016	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.028	-0.129	0.072
2017	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.042	0.047	0.101

2018	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.816	0.202	0.129
2019	J.C. Penney	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.041	0.103
2020	J.C. Penney	1.000	1.000	0.004	0.990	0.998
2021	J.C. Penney	-	1.000	-	-	-
2022	J.C. Penney	-	1.000	-	-	-

Source: model runs

- : not available. *: firm has ceased operations

The performance metrics for each model are listed in Table 13. In general, all three approaches yielded excellent accuracies. The Kappa value for the penalized maximum likelihood model suggests substantial agreement, but the PCA and Random Forest model Kappa values suggest good agreement (McHugh, 2012). All the models appeared to have excellent sensitivity, F1 scores, and AUC-ROC values. The PCA model appears to have weak precision, whereas the Random Forest model has weak specificity. Because the dataset does not use matched pairs, McNemar's test p-value can be ignored.

Table 13. Performance metrics by model approach

	Penalized Max. Likelihood	Random Forest	PCA
Accuracy	0.969	0.938	0.938
95% CI	(0.838, 0.999)	(0.792, 0.992)	(0.792, 0.992)
No Information Rate (NIR)	0.938	0.875	0.938
P-Value [Acc > NIR]	0.397	0.219	0.677
F1 score	0.983	1.000	0.966
Kappa	0.784	0.636	0.636
AUC-ROC	0.983	1.000	0.967
Precision	1.000	1.000	0.500
Mcnemar's Test P-Value	1.000	0.480	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
Sensitivity	0.967	1.000	0.933
Specificity	1.000	0.500	1.000
Pos Pred Value	1.000	0.933	1.000
Neg Pred Value	0.667	1.000	0.500
Prevalence	0.938	0.875	0.938
Detection Rate	0.906	0.875	0.875
Detection Prevalence	0.906	0.938	0.875
Balanced Accuracy	0.983	0.750	0.967
'Positive' Class	0.000	0.000	0.000

Source: model runs

4. Discussion

The analysis presented in this study suggests that predicting retail chain failure using revenue-based ratios is powerful. This study confirms the observations of Ceylan (2021), Keener (2013), and Rezende et al. (2017) that both internal and external factors provide predictive power. These results confirm that internal factors play a critical role in determining the likelihood of a firm failure. EBITDA and Long-term debt were not statistically significant predictors of failure on their own and not as a fraction of revenue. However, as fractions of revenue and as single predictors in logistic regression modeling, SGA/Revenue and EBITDA/Revenue were shown to be statistically significant predictors of failure. Throughout the three modeling approaches, EBITDA/Revenue, as a profitability measure, was identified as a consistent and strong predictor of failure, validating the observation by Li et al. (2022) regarding profitability. SGA/Revenue was also identified as a consistent and strong predictor of failure in Random Forest and PCA modeling. Curiously, while Cost of revenue/Revenue was not shown to be a statistically significant predictor or a feature that ranked with high importance in Random Forest modeling, this variable had the greatest factor loading in the second component of the PCA model, rivaling the loadings for EBITDA/Revenue. However, this observation suggests that the Cost of revenue/Revenue should not be overlooked as a potential predictor of failure in other settings. The differences in the importance of predictor variables using Random Forest and PCA can be explained by the differences between their approaches and assumptions. In general, this discrepancy stems from how each approach models the data and their underlying assumptions. First, while PCA relies on the linearity of relationships between the dependent and independent variables (Van Der Maaten, Postma, and Van Den Herik, 2009), Random Forest is a nonlinear approach that does not rely on these assumptions and can find important relationships in complex datasets (Aurel and Aldrich, 2011). Second, the goal of PCA is to find the best model by reducing the dimensionality of the dataset to the optimal number of components that explain the most variance with the least amount of error (Van Der Maaten, Postma, and Van Den Herik, 2009). However, the goal of Random Forest is to increase the predictive accuracy of a model and to reduce the dimensionality of large and complex datasets. Random Forest iteratively identifies the contribution of each variable or feature to model accuracy using the Gini importance of each feature, keeping those variables that are important to the predictive accuracy of a model, and eliminating irrelevant variables that do not add to the model's accuracy (Han, Guo, & Yu, 2016). As a result, Random Forest may identify some variables as being more or less important than those identified under PCA owing to the differences in approaches.

The results also highlight the importance of the external environment in predicting firm failure. The PCA and Random Forest analysis results point to the importance of the US annual rate of inflation and interest as consistent predictors of failure from macroeconomic influences, as observed by Kiyak and Pranckevičiūtė (2017). In logistic regression modeling, the rate of inflation was shown to be a statistically significant predictor of failure. While the ACSI score did not add predictive power in Random Forest modeling and was not statistically significant in logistic regression modeling, it was relevant in the principal component analysis. There is no question that customer satisfaction ratings service as a kind of barometer of sentiment that has some bearing on firm performance as suggested by Tuli and Bharadwaj (2009), Peng et al. (2014) and Fornell, Morgeson, and Hult (2016). However, the apparent overall lack of statistical importance of the ACSI score with respect to the prediction of firm failure validates the findings of Ittner, Larcker, and Taylor (2009) about the long-term role of customer satisfaction as a predictor of firm

performance. Finally, through logistic regression analysis, the COVID-19 pandemic dummy variable was shown to be a significant predictor of firm failure, the effect of which was to make retail firms much more likely to fail than if there was no pandemic. This result indicates that retail firms are highly vulnerable to external shocks. Therefore, greater attention must be paid to contingency planning and strategies to protect EBITDA and revenue if the operating environment is uncertain.

The performance of the three model approaches exceeds the accuracy estimates, as observed by Li et al. (2022), and generally aligns with those reported by Alaminos and Fernández (2016). The probability estimates generated by the failure model in Table 12 have several implications for predicting retail firm failure. First, although the Random Forest model generally tended to underestimate the probability of failure, each of the three modeling approaches appeared to agree when failure was likely to occur, suggesting that the approaches are generally accurate for the year in which failure will occur. Second, with the exception of the Random Forest model approach, the PCA and penalized maximum likelihood models appear to strongly signal one to two years before the firm fails, aligning with the observation by Arlov, Rankov, and Kotlica (2013) about early indicators of potential failure. This implies that these models are more sensitive than the Random Forest model with respect to internal and external firm factors and can provide valuable advance warnings to decision-makers. Such early signals can allow management to focus on problematic levels of debt, costs, and poor revenue management, given the large proportion of revenue consumed. Finally, while each modeling approach has its own merits, and because machine learning is still evolving as an analytical tool, the results of this study suggest that the use of PCA and logistic regression approaches for failure prediction is more precise and accurate than the Random Forest approach. This reaffirms the observation of Alaminos and Fernández (2016) that there is no single methodology that is completely precise, but may imply that certain approaches may be more appropriate according to the industry or regional setting. Indeed, the results of this study revealed minor misclassification, underlining the observation of Li (2012) that modeling often has unavoidable Type II errors. The result of the model runs for each year of firm operation implies that the demise of Sears Holdings was perhaps precipitated by other factors outside the factors examined in this study, such as technological change, as suggested by Redd and Vickerie (2017), and governance issues (Habib et al., 2020). The potential for failure of the other three firms was correctly signaled using the predictor variables in the models.

The use of revenue-based ratios as the basis for modeling retail firm failure in this study suggests that this is a good alternative to classical bankruptcy models that rely on asset-based ratios, such as the Z-score model. This approach can provide a risk factor that gives weight to revenue as a performance measure due to its importance to investors as indicated by Ghosh, Gu and Jain (2005), Huang, Marquardt and Zhang (2015), and Zhang (2005). Indeed, the use of revenue-based ratios and predictive modeling approaches illustrated in this study should complement and even validate any risk assessment. From a retail firm's perspective, given its vulnerability to certain internal and external factors, these ratios and model approaches should be used to benchmark performance levels and avoid failure. Furthermore, such revenue ratios and failure modeling provide an early warning for financial issues that can be proactively addressed by a distressed firm and its vendors, suppliers, and investors in a mutually beneficial way to avoid a costly future failure scenario. Moreover, as a means of mitigating losses, these tools can serve as the basis for adjusting the amount of credit that is extended and for changing the terms of future purchase orders by a distressed firm. For investors, these metrics can help signal that deeper discussions must take place regarding firm governance if failure is imminent, given that returns are ultimately threatened by poor performance. These insights are extremely valuable for enabling strategic decision-making for internal and external stakeholders.

5. Directions for future research

Retail failure remains a reality for retail firms. Additional research is required to enable the development of tools that use firm-level data to provide early warning signals of possible failures, similar to the failure prediction model presented in this study. Based on recent indicators, an advance warning that a retail chain may fail is valuable to investors and suppliers. Therefore, further research is required to validate the findings of this study and to use revenue-based measures to detect potential failures in other industrial sectors and regional settings. This implies the importance of competitive benchmarking of performance as an early indicator of success or failure, provided that this information can be tied to a firm's financial ratios.

Although only the COVID-19 pandemic was represented by a dummy variable in this study, additional investigations into random external and temporal shocks such as COVID-19 could leverage panel data and dynamic models in future studies. Given that publicly traded retail firms must identify and discuss all pertinent risk factors in their filings with the government, the risk of failure is therefore dependent on the speed at which the firm reacts to risk when it mitigates the financial impact. Therefore, I propose testable hypotheses for future research. First, does the speed of a firm's reaction mitigate failure? Using dynamic panel modeling, the dynamic property of how quickly firms react to the risk factors identified in 10-K filings can be used to identify whether firms that proactively modify their operations (for example, rather than reactively after a loss has occurred) to adapt to emerging risk factors successfully avoid failure. We hypothesize that firms that fail are more reactive and take more time to address the risk threats they identify in their filings. Third, do firms with stable boards and committee structures fail less than those with volatile boards and committees over time? Researchers can incorporate dummy variables to represent the completeness and turnover of the board of directors and committee structures over time in such models. Finally, does shareholder dissent or dissatisfaction and rogue investors compromise the stability of the firm over time and contribute to firm failure? The regularity of such events over time can be specified using these models through the analysis of shareholder votes, and the voting rights of shareholders.

Finally, future research must be conducted to identify the sources of variance that contribute to poor SGA control and the cost of revenue as triggers that could precipitate a process of failure for a firm. In particular, codifying governance practices and management structures, including any changes in governance, using data from 10-K filings would help to add a qualitative measure.

6. Limitations

As with any study, the limitations of this study must be acknowledged. First, because secondary data sources were used for firms' financial statements, ACSI scores, and macroeconomic data, changes in reporting or computation used by these sources may create hidden biases. This includes non-GAAP reporting of common financial information, resulting in potential inconsistencies. However, because 10-K filings are legal documents based on audited financial data, they should be viewed as reliable, and therefore pose no risk to generalizability. Second, the completeness of expected annual financial reporting when a firm ceases operations before a full year may present a limitation. In the case of data for J.C. Penney's final year, when only 10-Q was filed, rather than 10-K, full annual financial data could not be captured. Baldwin and Glezen (1992) "indicated that quarterly data are useful for predicting bankruptcy. There was no statistical evidence to suggest that the classification accuracy of the annual model was superior to that of the quarterly model" (p.269). Therefore, we can safely rely on quarterly financial data when results for a full year are unavailable, which should not lead to generalizability or reliability issues. Third, since ACSI scores were not available for Bed Bath and Beyond before 2015, financial data for that firm were collected from 2015 onward to match the available ACSI data, as was the case for each of the firms sampled in this study. Although this may be seen as a limitation, in that the sample periods for each firm are not exactly the same, the observations in the dataset reasonably represent a sample of retail firms' business activities during the broader period from 2013 to 2022. Thus, we expect the data to be reliable and generalizable to the entire retail industry. Fourth, as observed by Li (2012) and Alaminos and Fernández (2016), errors to some extent will generally persist in any kind of modeling, and no one modeling approach will always be completely accurate. Therefore, the results of modeling must be tempered with additional contextual information that

will guide decision-making. Finally, the author acknowledges that not all underlying factors of firm failure can be captured or accurately quantified because much of this competitive information is confidential to firms and is not publicly available beyond aggregated financial information. For this reason, my suggestions for future research should be explored to account for the unexplained variance in the prediction of retail failure.

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